

Nuclear observations to improve Climate research and GHG
emission estimates

Ambient gamma dose rate modelling

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In parallel to the measurement in the field campaigns, our project partners at Horia Hulubei National Institute of Physics and Nuclear Engineering – IFIN-HH (Romania) led by Anca Melintescu are developing models to describe the gamma dose background. The models are based on gamma radiation and radon concentration measurements from the ENA station on Graciosa (Azores, Portugal) as well as measurements at Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB)'s reference site. They describe the expected background gamma radiation for specific conditions.

Short-term fluctuations in the gamma dose rate are closely related to precipitation events because of the wash-out of radon progeny from the atmosphere. Radon together with its short-lived progeny is the primary contributor to short-term fluctuations in the environmental gamma radiation.

At the moment, the models can predict the expected background gamma radiation and its increase over the background due to precipitation and radon progeny wash-out. Now, they are further refined and new data is added. With the models, we will better understand natural variations and thereby improve environmental radiation models but also distinguish natural fluctuations from anthropogenic events.

For more details, see this preliminary report by IFIN-HH: <https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19705246>.